

Use of Vanadous Sulphate as a Reducing Agent. Part II. Estimation of Chlorates, Nitrates and Persulphates.

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In a previous communication (Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 198) it has been stated that chlorates, nitrates and persulphates are reduced by vanadous sulphate. In the present paper it is shown that under certain conditions the reduction is quantitative and that each of the above substances may be volumetrically estimated with a fair degree of accuracy. The substances are reduced with an excess of the reagent which is then titrated back with a standard solution of potassium permanganate. The vanadous salt is of course first standardised with the permanganate which oxidises it from divalent to the pentavalent state. With permanganate, the end-point is more sharp than with ferric alum and whenever the reduced product is without any action upon potassium permanganate, the latter should be preferred for back-titrations. An account of the preparation of the reagent and the general procedure for analysis have been given in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Estimation of Chlorate.

Chlorates are not quantitatively reduced by vanadous sulphate at the ordinary temperature, but on boiling it is completely reduced to chloride

0.5836 G. of pure NaClO_3 was dissolved in water and the solution was made up to 250 c.c. A known volume of this solution was mixed with 10-15 c.c. of dilute sulphuric acid in a 150 c.c. flask from which air has been expelled by carbon dioxide. The mixture was reduced with a known amount of VSO_4 solution by boiling for about 5 minutes in a current of carbon dioxide. The solution was cooled, diluted with water and then titrated with 0.1N- KMnO_4 solution.

To test the method chlorate was also estimated from the solution by reducing with FeSO_4 .

TABLE I.

VSO₄ soln. = 0.214N; KMnO₄ soln. = 0.1N. 1 C.c. of 0.1N-VSO₄
 = $\frac{\text{NaClO}_3}{6 \times 10^4}$ = 0.001775 g. of NaClO₃.

NaClO ₃ soln.	VSO ₄ soln.	KMnO ₄ soln.	Amount of NaClO ₃ found by VSO ₄ . FeSO ₄ .	
10 c.c.	12 c.c.	12.5 c.c.	100.2%	99.64%
10	20	29.7	99.6	„
10	12.5	13.55	100.4	„
25	25	20.8	99.45	„
25	25	20.7	99.8	„
25	30	31.3	100.2	„

Estimation of Nitrate.

The reaction between nitric acid and vanadous sulphate is far more complex than with chlorate or persulphate. It depends upon the relative concentrations of the reacting substances and temperature. It has been found that at ordinary temperature nitric oxide is formed when vanadium salt is slowly added to a moderately strong nitric acid solution. On the other hand, when the nitric acid is added to an excess of vanadous sulphate, no nitric oxide comes out. Probably the nitric oxide is absorbed by the excess of vanadous sulphate and remains in solution (*cf.* Friend, "Text Book of Inorganic Chemistry"). If however the nitric acid or a nitrate be added to a large excess of vanadous salt containing sufficient sulphuric acid and the mixture boiled in a current of carbon dioxide, the nitric acid is completely reduced to ammonia. Under these conditions by reducing to ammonia nitric acid can be estimated.

0.3211 G. of KNO₃ was dissolved in water and the solution was made up to 250 c.c.; 2 to 3 c.c. of H₂SO₄ (conc.) diluted with 25 c.c. of water were saturated with carbon dioxide in a 150 c.c. flask. A known volume of the VSO₄ solution was run into the flask from the burette and the KNO₃ solution was then added. The mixture was heated to boiling and kept at this temperature for about 5 minutes in a current of carbon dioxide. The solution was then cooled and titrated with the standard solution of KMnO₄. The VSO₄ solution was always freshly standardised under similar conditions so that any error due to impurities present in sulphuric acid or water might be eliminated.

TABLE II.

VSO_4 soln. = 0.2125N ; KMnO_4 soln. = 0.1N. 1 C.c. of 0.1N- VSO_4
 soln. = $\frac{\text{KN}(\text{O})_3}{8 \times 10^4} = 0.00126375$ g. of $\text{KN}(\text{O})_3$.

KNO_3 soln.	VSO_4 soln.	KMnO_4 soln.	KNO_3 found
5.0 c.c.	10 c.c.	16.20 c.c.	99.4%
10	20	32.35	99.8
10	20	32.40	99.4
10	25	43.00	99.6
15	30	48.65	99.1
15	20	27.30	99.7

Estimation of Persulphate.

Persulphuric acid is not completely reduced by vanadous salt either in the cold or when hot. If, however, it is treated with an excess of vanadous salt in the presence of a ferric salt, the per-acid is completely reduced to sulphate even at the ordinary temperature. Ferric salt is probably first reduced to ferrous salt which then acts on the persulphuric acid. The reactions may be represented by the following equations :

At the end of the reaction, the ferric iron will be in the ferrous state if there is enough V^{++} present in the solution. A part of the persulphuric is also directly reduced by vanadous salt. It is evident from the above equations that a small amount of Fe^{+++} is sufficient for the process of reduction to go on until all the persulphuric acid is reduced. To test this point experiments were carried out to find the minimum quantity of ferric salt that must be added to complete the reaction and it was found that 8 to 10 drops of a 0.1N ferric alum solution were necessary for this purpose.

5.5933 G. of Merck's (G.R.) ammonium persulphate were dissolved in 500 c.c. of water. A known volume of this solution was taken in a 150 c.c. flask from which air has been removed by a stream of carbon

dioxide. A few c.c. of ferric alum solution were added and then a known volume of VSO_4 solution was run into the flask; 15 to 20 c.c. of H_2SO_4 were added and the mixture was allowed to stand for 2-3 minutes in a current of carbon dioxide. The solution was then titrated with the standard $KMnO_4$ solution.

To test the results the persulphuric acid was also estimated by reducing with ferrous sulphate.

TABLE III.

$VSO_4 = 0.214N$; $KMnO_4$ soln. = $0.1N$; Ferric alum soln. = $0.1N$.

$$\text{r.c.c. of } 0.1N\text{-}VSO_4\text{ soln.} = \frac{(NH_4)_2S_2O_8}{2 \times 10^4} = 0.01141\text{g. of } (NH_4)_2S_2O_8.$$

Persulphate soln	Ferric alum soln.	VSO_4 soln.	$KMnO_4$ soln.	Amount of persulphate found by VSO_4 , $FeSO_4$.	
10 c.c.	2 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	11.65 c.c.	99.5%	99.32%
10	5	10.1	11.9	99.1	„
10	1	10.0	11.7	99.0	„
25	10	25.0	29.2	99.15	„
25	2	20.0	18.4	99.55	„
25	1	25.5	30.25	99.2	„

SUMMARY.

1. Chlorates, nitrates and persulphates may be estimated by introducing a known quantity into an excess of vanadous sulphate solution and titrating back the excess with a standard solution of potassium permanganate.

2. Chlorates and nitrates are reduced by vanadous sulphate to chlorides and ammonia respectively by boiling in presence of sulphuric acid in a current of carbon dioxide. In the case of persulphate the reduction is complete only in the presence of a little ferric salt.